

SEISMEC

NEWSWAVE

Dear reader,

The SEISMEC Newswave is back, bringing you the latest updates, news, and activities of the SEISMEC project.

As we step into 2026, we are excited to announce that SEISMEC is now **entering its third year!** We are all looking forward to welcoming the new year, where our project pilots will continue to generate human-centric solutions, our participation in key events has already been discussed, and our collaboration activities will continue to grow! And this is just a preview of 2026.

This December marks our **two-year anniversary!** Reaching the halfway point of the SEISMEC project is an exciting milestone, giving us the opportunity to reflect on the progress made and the activities driving us forward.

[Read our full two-year reflection](#) to explore our achievements, insights, and what's coming next.

How can we ensure that technology empowers people rather than replaces them?

This question lay at the heart of the SEISMEC project. Our work throughout the project's duration is to place humans at the centre of Industry 5.0 and to ensure ethical, human-centred and balanced applications of AI. Jan Laurijssen met with Professor Jason Pridmore for an inspiring conversation on how people and technology can grow together.

[KNOW MORE](#)

SEISMEC 2nd Online Workshop: Flip the script: Powering worker participation in the design and implementation of technology

What role should employees have in the design and implementation of workplace technologies?

This was the key question that guided our second online workshop, held on 11 November 2025. The SEISMEC approach to enhancing worker involvement in adopting technological solutions at workplace was thoroughly explained through detailed presentations, scenario-based activities, and live discussions. Explore every detail and watch the full recording, along with the dedicated Knowledge pills we created for a smooth navigation in our second workshop.

Guidebook for Worker Participation

Workers are at the heart of shaping the processes and systems that impact their work.

Explore the SEISMEC methodological approach for worker participation, combining concepts, principles, and techniques. The step-by-step process integrates design principles, organisational dynamics, and stakeholder collaboration to ensure meaningful and sustainable participation.

The result? Workers actively involved in the process, not just heard.

[CHECK THE STEPS & THE FULL GUIDEBOOK](#)

SEISMEC Pilots in action

October opened with live demonstrations during the General Assembly in Thessaloniki, where selected pilots were presented on site and partners had the chance to test technologies or observe how they will be used in real working environments. Later in the month, partners from [Zagreb Airport](#), [InfraPlan](#), [CERTH](#), [Technische Universität Berlin](#), [DFAI](#) and [Erasmus University Rotterdam](#) met at [Zagreb Airport](#) to review progress and jointly plan the next steps for the automated Foreign Object Debris inspection pilot.

[EXPLORE THE PILOT DEMOS](#)

[WHAT HAPPENED IN ZAGREB](#)

SEISMEC around the Globe!

At every opportunity, the SEISMEC partners are actively participating in meaningful events, spreading the word about the project's aims and results!

In June, SEISMEC joined EUWIN, [BRIDGES 5.0](#) and BROADVOICE EU in Leuven for a co-organised conference on the [future of work, employee voice, and Industry 5.0](#), highlighting that in order for Industry 5.0 to succeed, it must be shaped in partnership with the workforce and those who represent them. In September, SEISMEC took part in the Sociotechnical Organisational Design Conference in Trondheim, Norway, contributing to discussions on how organisational structures and technological systems can support more resilient and people-centred workplaces.

To round off the season, the consortium gathered in October in Thessaloniki for its [General Assembly Meeting](#), reviewing pilot progress, milestones and setting the next steps ahead.

But more events are coming soon! Where will the SEISMEC project be in January 2026?

On January 29th from 11:00-13:00 CET, SEISMEC will join an interactive online roundtable, bringing together leading voices from the EU HORIZON projects [AIREDEGIO](#), [BRIDGES 5.0](#), [PROSPECTS 5.0](#), SEISMEC, [SKILLABILITY](#), and [UPSKILL](#) to explore the evolving landscape of Industry 5.0.

REGISTER TODAY

SEISMEC reading corner

Explore the latest SEISMEC publications, including *SMART Work Design and Modern Sociotechnical Theory. A marriage made in heaven?* and *Ladder Walking Detection via Action Recognition for Enhancing Worker Safety in Construction*, together with the *newly published deliverables*.

[READ MORE](#)

What's next? And that's a wrap for SEISMEC in 2025! We are excited for the second half of the project, with various planned activities and results.

Wishing you a restful holiday season and we look forward to reconnecting in 2026.

SEISMEC

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